

APPEARANCES OF REMOTE SENSING FOR TEACHING PEDAGOGY OF ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION

Abstract:

Pedagogy method is the strategy behind the specialty of instructing. It thinks about how understudies learn and utilizes that information to foster methods of reasoning, approaches, and strategies for the study hall. Only one out of every odd instructor has a teaching method. Particularly at the school level, numerous teachers don't get formal preparation in how to educate. Changing this worldview requires proactive instructors and foundations focused on understudy achievement. The initial step is finding out about various instructive strategies. Instructive information can assist any instructor with turning into a more viable teacher. The more methodologies you comprehend as an educator, the more viable you can be in planning coursework to address your understudies' issues. In geospatial innovation, remote sensing gathers tests that are discharged through electromagnetic radiation and reflected from the World's barometrical, earthbound, and amphibian biological systems. This takes into account the recognition and checking of the actual qualities of a region without the need to connect with the area. The topic "**Appearances Of Remote Sensing For Teaching Pedagogy Of Environmental Education**" the radiation that is reflected or delivered by a thing or the region around it very well might be assembled utilizing aloof sensors, which are sensors that respond to outside upgrades. Reflected daylight is the most common sort of radiation source that is checked utilizing latent remote detecting methods. Charge-coupled gadgets, radiometers, film photography, and infrared are a couple of notable instances of famous kinds of remote detecting. The study of the climate did a ways off by means of satellite imaging, elevated photography, and radar is a remote detecting climate. By taking readings of electromagnetic waves, distant sensors can acquire data. Distributing research discoveries on the hypothesis, science, applications, and innovation of remote sensing of the climate offers a support to the local area of individuals who work in remote sensing.

Key words:

Remote Sensing, Geospatial Innovation, Socio-Cultural, Natural Resource, Population, Environmental Education, Pedagogy method

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Introduction

Improvement is at the core of Learning Diaries and we comprehend that guardians would rather not miss a snapshot of this intriguing excursion. We maintain that a youngster's advancement should be effectively open so express boundless viewpoints as a component of our foundation. This helps educators and guardians to catch kids at the time, and develop an image of their movement after some time. We remove the issue from noticing, so you can return to getting a charge out of time with your kid. For nursery school proprietors, our way to deal with learning is custom fitted around you. Whether you're involving an *EYFS* system or the Educational program for Greatness, the Learning Diaries stage can be customized to suit your particular requirements. Furthermore, there's compelling reason need to stress over desk work. With our web-based instrument, you can see a full dashboard of your staff as well as having the option to get to kids' profiles. This assists you with remaining coordinated and on target. Perception satellites of the Earth, frequently known as remote detecting satellites, are one more name for remote detecting satellites. They may likewise be utilized for natural checking, meteorology, and planning, notwithstanding their job as spy satellites. The most predominant kind is Earth-imaging satellites, which catch pictures from space very like those taken from planes. Remote detecting of the climate is utilized by Some satellites that can do as such without creating pictures, similarly as with GNSS radio occultation. Dynamic and detached remote detecting are the two essential classifications of remote detecting, each sorted by the wellspring of sign used to research an item. Dynamic remote detecting gadgets produce their wellspring of outflow or light to work, instead of uninvolved instruments, which rely upon the reflected one. It is useful to obtain a forward-thinking land use example of wide areas at any second utilizing remote detecting geology information. This information may likewise be utilized to screen changes that happen every once in a while. Guides of streets, black-top circumstances, and the limits of wetlands may be in every way raised to date with its assistance. Local organizers and chairmen utilize this data while figuring out arrangement measures to work with far reaching development across the area.

Background of study

The performance of weather conditions estimating in India utilizes remote detecting innovation. What's more, it is used to give individuals advance notice of moving toward typhoons. Deforestation, the disintegration of ripe grounds, contamination in the climate, desertification, eutrophication of colossal water bodies, and oil slicks from oil big haulers are a portion of the natural issues that might be explored with its assistance. The utilization of remote detecting considers the examination of harm welcomed on by cataclysmic events like seismic tremors, volcanoes, avalanches, floods, and the liquefying of ice in polar regions. The utilization of remote detecting may frequently be utilized while endeavoring to figure the coming of cataclysmic events. The utilization of remote detecting information is significant for recognizing petroleum product holds, quickly planning lineament and structural guides, distinguishing regions for quarrying minerals, and refreshing existing land maps. Furthermore, remote detecting information is valuable for refreshing existing geographical guides.

Significant of the study

These varieties of information might be put to use during the time spent concocting game plans for utilization both when normal calamities. The framework is particularly significant for ecological checking and the administration of normal assets. Also, it investigations people's impact on the general climate. Oceanography is another field that might profit from remote detecting since it screens sea flow, temperature, and wave levels to get a more profound comprehension of sea assets. The technique has applications in topography, mineral investigation, farming, and ranger service. The goal of the photos acquired by satellites could frequently be too low to even consider recognizing small differentiating locales and do exhaustive planning. Deciphering the information got is troublesome, tedious, and costly, and the estimation vulnerability is frequently huge. Remote detecting is the study

of getting data about the world's surface utilizing high-flying satellites and airplane. Data acquired from remote detecting furnishes leaders with significant and broad information for planning, natural checking, and calamity the board. Remote detecting has a great many applications in dealing with the climate.

Review of related literature

- **Congalton, Russell G.; Green, Kass (2019).**, Land-cover and land-use maps are expected for some applications, for example, districts arranging, scene arranging, and scene nature, horticultural administration, and ranger service. Electromagnetic energy arriving at the world's surface from the Sun is reflected, assimilated or communicated.
- **Christopher D. (February 2020).**, A fundamental suspicion made in remote detecting is that particular review targets (various sorts of soils, water having various levels of pollutants, rocks of various lithologies, or vegetation of different species) have an individual and trademark way of communicating with episode radiation that is depicted by the unearthly reaction of that study target. The otherworldly reflectance can be impacted by many factors, for example, soil supplements, the development phase of the vegetation, the shade of the dirt (which might be impacted by ongoing atmospheric conditions).
- **Howard, A.; et al. (2015).**, In certain occurrences, the connection between episode radiation and earth's surface article will be not quite the same as time to time, for example, may be normal on account of vegetation as it changes from the leafing stage, through development and, at long last to senescence. The term 'unearthly mark' is at times used to portray the phantom reaction bend for a review target. Satellite symbolism and standardized distinction vegetation index (NDVI) advancements are utilized to screen worldwide food supplies. Sound harvests region reflect green where different regions reflect red or blue.
- **Stehman, S. (2019).**, The strength of yields can be estimated utilizing remote detecting applications so just about 10% of compost, cash and time can be saved. Dynamic and uninvolved sensors of a satellite in space are utilized to decide soil dampness content. Many studies of the planet, for example, water cycle, flood, and dry season depend on the substance of soil dampness.
- **Zhao, Kaiguang; Suarez, Juan C; Garcia, Mariano; Hu, Tongxi; Wang, Cheng; Londo, Alexis (2018).**, Remote Sensing is accustomed to foreseeing crop creation and yield over a given field and decide the amount of the harvest will be reaped under the particular circumstances. The scientist can foresee the harvest amount that will be created in given farmland over a given timeframe. In case of yield harm or harvest progress, remote detecting innovation can be utilized to enter the farmland and decide precisely the amount of a given yield has been harmed or under pressure and the advancement of the excess yield in the ranch.
- **Innocenti, Fabrizio; Robinson, Rod; Gardiner, Tom; Finlayson, Andrew; Connor, Andy (2017).**, The yield can likewise be recognized utilizing remote detecting innovation particularly in situations where the harvest under perception is secretive or shows a few strange qualities. The information of the harvest is gathered and taken to the labs where different parts of the yield including the yield culture are considered.

Objectives of the study

1. To know the Natural aspects of remort sensing on Environment
2. To know the Socio-cultural aspects of remort sensing on Environment

Research question of study

1. What are the Natural aspects of remote sensing on Environment ?
2. What are the Socio-cultural aspects of remote sensing on Environment ?

Analysis and Interpretation

➤ Natural aspects of remote sensing on Environment

Pedagogy refers to the method and practices of a teacher

With this methodology, the educator is at the focal point of all learning rehearses. It centers around the utilization of direct guidance, and talk based examples to convey various subjects to understudies. The hypothesis of Behaviorism in a homeroom got from educational exploration by Thorndike (1911), Pavlov (1927) and Skinner (1957). Behaviorist instructional method accepts the educator ought to be the sole power figure, and leads the example. This thoroughly conflicts with the thoughts of Piaget, and in certain faculties Vygotsky, who accept youngsters should guide some or the entirety of their own learning. Behaviorism accepts information ought to be conveyed in an educational program where each subject is instructed discretely. This differentiations with point based realizing which gives cross curricular chances to permit understudies to investigate topics in more profundity. They can then improve associations between various areas of learning. In an illustration utilizing a behaviorist educational methodology, practices would incorporate addressing, displaying and show, and choral reiteration. Every movement is 'apparent' and organized and is driven by the educator at the front. Nonetheless, there might be times during the illustration, where there is a slight shift and the understudy turns into the focal point of the movement. Youngsters then, at that point, have the chance to show their own figuring out how to the remainder of the class.

Analysis and The section of Farming and Forests

Distant sensors and GIS applications are amazing assets for observing forested regions in the climate. Actual checking of backwoods is trying because of the chance of wild creatures and many thick shrubberies in many woods. The remote detecting strategy is an elective technique for observing these conditions. Scientists place high-flying satellites and artworks over the objective regions to notice any natural changes.

Water Resources and controlling

Water asset the board involves arranging, creating, and dealing with the ideal utilization of water assets. The public authority and other policymakers have set up different measures to safeguard water bodies globally. In any case, residents neglect to notice these actions and rules since there is no on location checking and perceptions. Fortunately, far off sensors can now be utilized to screen exercises around water bodies.

Air and Water Quality and environmental impacts

Water and air are the most key things in the climate . The security of both water and air should be kept up with consistently. The remote detecting strategy oversees air and water quality in the climate by distinguishing the reasons for their contamination and giving data about their quality support to general society. Public and confidential actual designs like streets, spans, rail lines, electric frameworks, and water are parts of the climate that should be observed much of the time. It may not be simple for cops to watch everywhere; the remote detecting procedure was acquainted with tackle such difficulties. Satellite sensors are utilized to record and take pictures of the multitude of exercises close to the frameworks. Information from the sensors is dissected, checked, and used to design better overseeing framework. Regular assets like oil, coal, water, woods, and gaseous petrol are significant; consequently can be effortlessly messed with through shoplifting and abuse.

Remote sensing and climate

Remote detecting strategies are utilized to safeguard these assets by keep every one of the exercises in the climate. Sensors enormously decrease the maltreatment and burglary of regular assets in ecological administration. Regular dangers like floods and dry season occasions are an extraordinary danger to the climate. They should be checked and controlled when their event. Remote detecting devices prove to be useful in controlling flames, dry spell occasions, desertification, and floods. For example, on the off chance that there is a fire episode, satellite sensors permit officers to notice the impacted region easily and to control the fire from spreading. Seaside checking includes gathering information about the waterfront climate. Far off sensors are utilized to screen coastline changes and measure seas' temperatures in the beach front climate. Then again, Geographic Data Frameworks assist with doing advancements, arranging processes, and compelling administration of the waterfront zone.

Soil Dampness Information

The dirt layer is imperative for farming and ecological development; the dirt is additionally significant in estimating climate and catastrophic events for natural administration. A critical area of exploration right now occurring in the remote detecting field is the proportion of soil dampness which involves estimating the main 5 cm of the earth surface. NASA's dirt dampness Dynamic Aloof (SMAP) Mission utilizes satellites to recover information about soil dampness following 2 to 3 days.

Vegetation Observing and perceptions

The most fitting record that examiners use in vegetation checking is the NDVI Far off sensors use NDVI to quantify the distinction between Close Infrared and red light reflected and consumed by plants. Information from the perceptions is utilized in horticulture, cultivating, and forest the management .

➤ **Socio-cultural aspects of remort sensing on Environment**

Urban Planning and Remote Sensing

Metropolitan arranging includes planning, supporting, and carrying out systems that influence the social effects of the metropolitan climate. Legitimate arranging is expected to stay away from clogged conditions in metropolitan places. In metropolitan preparation, the remote detecting method contributes to take pictures of the absolute region covered by the metropolitan. Pictures from the sensors are valuable in the arranging system.

Usual Appraisal and Territory Protection

Remote detecting is helpful in recognizing the reason for deforestation, volcanoes, contaminations, floods, and other regular perils. Significant data from these examinations is tried to forestall more risks from now on. Sensors are likewise valuable in keep every one of the exercises in a given region to keep up with the wellbeing of environments.

Including Individual Population and Grasping Territory

Scientists are presently going to satellites for counting creature populaces. For instance, getting dependable includes for polar bears in the Arctic is difficult. However, for transient examinations, they don't miscalculate polar bears as large stones in the event that they move in every scene. So presently, satellite symbolism is a device to follow Icy untamed life like polar bears in light of the distance and calculated requirements.

Furthermore, here's one more utilization of having dependable and precise land cover information. We can concentrate on creature living spaces and safeguard their territory type. For instance, discontinuity from street foundation can altogether affect jeopardized creatures. Utilizing GPS telemetry, we can

comprehend which environments creatures involve and moderate them utilizing natural surroundings appropriateness models.

Utilizing trilateration and a star grouping of satellites broadcasting signals is the means by which GPS framework frameworks work. For instance, lightweight telemetry restraints get GPS flags and can follow the significant distances relocating creatures travel. Since birds frequently live in wetlands and backwoods, natural life directors utilize light location and going , multispectral and radar to show woods properties like vertical design and phenology.

Land Use Planning & Remote Sensing

This remote detecting innovation's abilities extend past conventional instruments. This gives exact and current information on how land is used and its surface qualities. This data helps with settling on informed conclusions about land the executives, metropolitan preparation, and normal asset use. Remote detecting methods, for example, satellite symbolism and aeronautical photography, catch pictures of Earth's surface. These pictures are then dissected to recognize different land cover types, similar to timberlands, horticulture, or metropolitan regions, and land use designs, like private, business, or modern zones. Usually the land is profoundly inclined to changes over the long run. With the utilization of this innovation, it is not difficult to recognize changes that continue to happen, similar to deforestation, never-ending suburbia, and so on. Then again, remote detecting assists specialists with arranging maintainable land the executives methodologies. For instance, it can feature regions inclined to disintegration or living space misfortune, considering designated preservation endeavors.

Major findings of study

This component works by examining the reflected or produced electromagnetic radiation from crops, which shows their wellbeing and development status. In the wake of deciphering this information through the related advancements like and Information Analysis, ranchers can go with informed choices in regards to trim administration rehearses. This can go from changing compost application to carrying out designated bother control measures, and so forth.

- This component considers an extensive comprehension of land elements for the specialists. It likewise urges the modern world to really offset advancement with natural preservation.
- We know that around 71% of the world's surface is covered with water. Nonetheless, assuming that we think about the usable water assets, they are tragically restricted.
- To this end the advanced modern scene has been compelled to focus on delivering poisons into streams. Nonetheless, water asset the executives isn't something that we can mess with, as it requires cautious perception and investigation.
- Remote detecting innovation helps the climate by supporting water asset the executives in different ways. In one manner, it evaluates water quality, screen water bodies, distinguish contamination sources, and guide wetlands. We realize that this innovation works by using satellites or airplane outfitted with sensors to catch information about water-related boundaries like temperature, turbidity, and compound creation.
- In another manner, the gathered data is then handled to produce guides and reports demonstrating the wellbeing of water bodies and expected wellsprings of contamination.
- As it controls the specialists to screen such changes after some time, remote detecting permits them to distinguish regions in danger of defilement or consumption. This guides compelling water asset the board methodologies.

- Allow us to make sense of this with a model. It can identify hurtful algal blossoms in lakes or follow contaminations in streams, which recommends opportune mediations to safeguard sea-going Environments and guarantee safe drinking water supplies.
- This resembles cut out of the same cloth. In one manner, it assists save with watering assets. In another manner, it adjust the supportability and smooth working of modern cycles.
- Horticulture is the core of a nation and the job of its kin. Without this, there would be no food on our tables.
- To this end the specialists focus on getting this industry far from its likely weight. In that sense, remote detecting innovation gives important help to ranchers and rural specialists.
- How could this be made conceivable, As this incorporates satellites or concentrated airplane furnished with sensors, remote detecting catches information on crop wellbeing, yield assessment, water system advancement, and the discovery of nuisance pervasions or infections.
- Then again, agrarian specialists can use this data for strategy making and asset designation to help feasible cultivating practices and improve food security drives.
- It is obvious that remote detecting innovation adds to a better and more practical food framework, all while keeping the modern supportability guarantee alive however much it can.

Conclusion

Modern zones are number one on the rundown of regions that have the greatest measure of air contamination on the planet. Air contamination happens when processing plants, mines, and transportation discharge poisonous substances up high. These poisons can cause some serious medical problems, for example, respiratory illnesses, disease, diminished lung capability, asthma, and so on. We shouldn't fail to remember that they can likewise be unsafe to the climate, which will cause corrosive downpour and environmental change. Presently let us expand on how the last option helps the climate by defending the air. Utilizing satellites and concentrated sensors, remote detecting accumulates information on different poisons in the environment, like particulate matter, nitrogen dioxide, and ozone. While examining this information, researchers and states can follow contamination levels, recognize wellsprings of defilement, and assess the adequacy of air quality administration procedures. This strategy makes it conceivable to make a brief move to lessen contamination and shield general wellbeing from breathing issues and other adverse consequences of low air quality. Likewise, information from remote detecting assists with understanding the spatial and topographical dissemination of toxins, which proposes centered reactions in the districts where contamination is generally serious.

References

1. **Achard, F (2002).** "Determination of deforestation rates of the world's humid tropical forests". *Science*. 297 (5583): 999–1002. Bibcode:2002Sci...297..999A. doi:10.1126/science.1070656. PMID 12169731.
2. **Ambrosio Flores, L (2000).** "Land cover estimation in small areas using ground survey and remote sensing". *Remote Sensing of Environment*. 74 (2): 240–248. Bibcode:2000RSEnv..74..240F. doi:10.1016/S0034-4257(00)00114-0.
3. **C. Bayindir; J. D. Frost; C. F. Barnes (January 2018).** "Assessment and enhancement of SAR noncoherent change detection of sea-surface oil spills". *IEEE J. Ocean. Eng.* 43 (1): 211–220. Bibcode:2018IJOE...43..211B. doi:10.1109/JOE.2017.2714818. S2CID 44706251.
4. **C. L. Parkinson , (2010),** A. Ward, M. D. King (Eds.) *Earth Science Reference Handbook – A Guide to NASA's Earth Science Program and Earth Observing Satellite Missions*, National

- Aeronautics and Space Administration Washington, D. C. Available at http://eosps0.gsfc.nasa.gov/ftp_docs/2006ReferenceHandbook.pdf Archived 15 April 2010 at the Wayback Machine
5. **Carfagna, E. (2005)**. "Using remote sensing for agricultural statistics". *International Statistical Review*. 73 (3): 389–404. doi:10.1111/j.1751-5823.2005.tb00155.x.
 6. **Christopher D. (February 2020)**. "Remote sensing of night lights: A review and an outlook for the future". *Remote Sensing of Environment*. 237: 111443. Bibcode:2020RSEnv.23711443L. doi:10.1016/j.rse.2019.111443. hdl:10871/40052. S2CID 214254543.
 7. **Congalton, Russell G.; Green, Kass (2019)**. *Assessing the Accuracy of Remotely Sensed Data: Principles and Practices, Third Edition (3 ed.)*. Boca Raton: CRC Press. doi:10.1201/9780429052729. ISBN 978-0-429-05272-9.
 8. **Corradino, Claudia; Ganci, Gaetana; Bilotta, Giuseppe; Cappello, Annalisa; Del Negro, Ciro; Fortuna, Luigi (2019)**. "Smart Decision Support Systems for Volcanic Applications". *Energies*. 12 (7): 1216. doi:10.3390/en12071216.
 9. **Corradino, Claudia; Ganci, Gaetana; Cappello, Annalisa; Bilotta, Giuseppe; Héroult, Alexis; Del Negro, Ciro (2019)**. "Mapping Recent Lava Flows at Mount Etna Using Multispectral Sentinel-2 Images and Machine Learning Techniques". *Remote Sensing*. 11 (16): 1916. Bibcode:2019RemS...11.1916C. doi:10.3390/rs11161916.
 10. **Foody, G.M. (1994)**. "Estimation of tropical forest extent and regenerative stage using remotely sensed data". *Journal of Biogeography*. 21 (3): 223–244. Bibcode:1994JBiog..21..223F. doi:10.2307/2845527. JSTOR 2845527.
 11. **Gamon, John A. (2018)**. "Plant spectral diversity integrates functional and phylogenetic components of biodiversity and predicts ecosystem function". *Nature Ecology & Evolution*. 2 (6): 976–982. Bibcode:2018NatEE...2..976S. doi:10.1038/s41559-018-0551-1. ISSN 2397-334X. PMID 29760440. S2CID 256718584.
 12. **Goldberg, A.; Stann, B.; Gupta, N. (July 2003)**. "Multispectral, Hyperspectral, and Three-Dimensional Imaging Research at the U.S. Army Research Laboratory" (PDF). *Proceedings of the International Conference on International Fusion [6th]*. 1: 499–506.
 13. **GRAS-SAF (2009)**, Product User Manual, GRAS Satellite Application Facility, Version 1.2.1, 31 March 2009. Available at http://www.grassaf.org/general-documents/products/grassaf_pum_v121.pdf Archived 26 July 2011 at the Wayback Machine
 14. **Grigoriev A.N. (2015)**. "Method of radiometric distortion correction of multispectral data for the earth remote sensing". *Scientific and Technical Journal of Information Technologies, Mechanics and Optics*. 15 (4): 595–602. doi:10.17586/2226-1494-2015-15-4-595-602.
 15. **Howard, A.; et al. (2015)**. "Remote sensing and habitat mapping for bearded capuchin monkeys (*Sapajus libidinosus*): landscapes for the use of stone tools". *Journal of Applied Remote Sensing*. 9 (1): 096020. doi:10.1117/1.JRS.9.096020. S2CID 120031016.
 16. **Hu, Liuru; Navarro-Hernández, María I.; Liu, Xiaojie; Tomás, Roberto; Tang, Xinming; Bru, Guadalupe; Ezquerro, Pablo; Zhang, Qingtao (2022)**. "Analysis of regional large-gradient land subsidence in the Alto Guadalentín Basin (Spain) using open-access aerial LiDAR datasets". *Remote Sensing of Environment*. 280: 113218. Bibcode:2022RSEnv.28013218H. doi:10.1016/j.rse.2022.113218. hdl:10045/126163. ISSN 0034-4257.

17. **Innocenti, Fabrizio; Robinson, Rod; Gardiner, Tom; Finlayson, Andrew; Connor, Andy (2017)**. "Differential Absorption Lidar (DIAL) Measurements of Landfill Methane Emissions". *Remote Sensing*. 9 (9): 953. Bibcode:2017RemS....9..953I. doi:10.3390/rs9090953.
18. **Makki, Ihab; Younes, Rafic; Francis, Clovis; Bianchi, Tiziano; Zucchetti, Massimo (1 February 2017)**. "A survey of landmine detection using hyperspectral imaging". *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*.
19. **Mills, J.P.; et al. (1997)**. "Photogrammetry from Archived Digital Imagery for Seal Monitoring". *The Photogrammetric Record*. 15 (89): 715–724. doi:10.1111/0031-868X.00080. S2CID 140189982.
20. **NASA (1986)**, Report of the EOS data panel, Earth Observing System, Data and Information System, Data Panel Report, Vol. IIA., NASA Technical Memorandum 87777, June 1986, 62 pp. Available at <http://hdl.handle.net/2060/19860021622> Archived 27 October 2021 at the Wayback Machine
21. **Nicole J. (2021)**. "No place to hide: Rare plant detection through remote sensing". *Diversity and Distributions*. 27 (6): 948–961. Bibcode:2021DivDi..27..948C. doi:10.1111/ddi.13244. ISSN 1366-9516. S2CID 233886263.
22. **Pettorelli, Nathalie (2016)**. Skidmore, Andrew; Chauvenet, Alienor (eds.). "Satellite remote sensing to monitor species diversity: potential and pitfalls". *Remote Sensing in Ecology and Conservation*. 2 (1): 25–36. Bibcode:2016RSEC....2...25R. doi:10.1002/rse2.9. hdl:11585/720672. ISSN 2056-3485. S2CID 59446258.
23. **Stehman, S. (2013)**. "Estimating Area from an Accuracy Assessment Error Matrix". *Remote Sensing of Environment*. 132 (132): 202–211. Bibcode:2013RSEnv.132..202S. doi:10.1016/j.rse.2013.01.016.
24. **Stehman, S. (2019)**. "Key issues in rigorous accuracy assessment of land cover products". *Remote Sensing of Environment*. 231 (231). Bibcode:2019RSEnv.23111199S. doi:10.1016/j.rse.2019.05.018.
25. **Stewart, J.E.; et al. (2014)**. "Finescale ecological niche modeling provides evidence that lactating gray seals (*Halichoerus grypus*) prefer access to fresh water in order to drink" (PDF). *Marine Mammal Science*.
26. **Taylor, J (1997)**. *Regional Crop Inventories in Europe Assisted by Remote Sensing: 1988-1993. Synthesis Report*. Luxembourg: Office for Publications of the EC.
27. **Twiss, S.D.; et al. (2001)**. "Topographic spatial characterisation of grey seal *Halichoerus grypus* breeding habitat at a sub-seal size spatial grain". *Ecography*. 24 (3): 257–266. doi:10.1111/j.1600-0587.2001.tb00198.x.
28. **Wang, Ran; Gamon, John A. (2019)**. "Remote sensing of terrestrial plant biodiversity". *Remote Sensing of Environment*. 231: 111218. Bibcode:2019RSEnv.23111218W. doi:10.1016/j.rse.2019.111218. ISSN 0034-4257. S2CID 197567301.
29. **Zhang, Chuanrong; Li, Xinba (2022)**. "Land Use and Land Cover Mapping in the Era of Big Data". *Land*. 11 (10): 1692. doi:10.3390/land11101692.
30. **Zhao, Kaiguang; Suarez, Juan C; Garcia, Mariano; Hu, Tongxi; Wang, Cheng; Londo, Alexis (2018)**. "Utility of multitemporal lidar for forest and carbon monitoring: Tree growth, biomass dynamics, and carbon flux". *Remote Sensing of Environment*. 204: 883–897. Bibcode:2018RSEnv.204..883Z. doi:10.1016/j.rse.2017.09.007.

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31. **Zhen, Z (2013)**. "Impact of training and validation sample selection on classification accuracy and accuracy assessment when using reference polygons in object-based classification". *International Journal of Remote Sensing*. 34 (19): 6914–6930. Bibcode:2013IJRS...34.6914Z. doi:10.1080/01431161.2013.810822.